

ON SOME FACTORS AFFECTING THE REALISATION OF

GLASS FIBRE STRENGTH IN COMPOUND MATERIALS

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Out of all grades of modern fibres, glass fibres are the most popular reinforcing material to form high-strength compounds.

It is known that glass is the classical example of fragile matter on which the discrepancy of theoretical and technical strength is observed. Only a small part of potential strength of glass is used in practice, while its theoretical strength is predicted about 1000-2000 kg/mm²; in fused quartz with high strength of interatomic structural bonds this strength exceeds 2000 kg/mm². From our point of view the effect of high technical strength of glass fibre as compared with "mass" glass is determined by the more isotropic structure of the high-temperature glass melt out of which fibres are made, the high rate of their cooling and by the reduction of micro-defects and microcracks appearing on the fibre surface during the process of their formation.

The highest level of strength is achieved in fused quartz fibres and refractory fibres made of magnesia-alumosilicate glass, which is determined by the high strength of their structural bonds. Our experimental data (Table I) prove that under low temperatures, for example in liquid nitrogen when the process of microcracks formation is slowed down and the absorptive effect of air humidity is eliminated, the maximum value of strength in fibres is 1700-1800 kg/mm², which approximates the calculated theoretical strength of glass and

Table I
The strength of quartz and glass fibres under different test conditions

No.	Grade of fibre dia. 5-7μ	strength, kg/mm ²				
		from bobbin "virgin" in liquid nitrogen				
		aver.	max.	aver.	aver.	max.
1.	Quartz	350	600	650-700	700-1400	1800
2.	Magnesia-alumosilicate	500	600	600	700	1700
3.	High modulus of cordierite composition	450	500	500	600	1100
4.	Alkali-free alumoborsilicate "E"	280	350	380	450	800

x) depending on quality of quartz

fused quartz. [1] For high-modulus glass fibres with microglass crystal structure the maximum value of strength in liquid nitrogen does not exceed 1100 kg/mm². [2]

It is determined that the average strength of quartz and refractory glass fibres, tested in liquid nitrogen, equals 650-700 kg/mm² and approximately corresponds to the strength of these fibres tested in "virgin" state. [3] The further reduction of strength in quartz and glass fibres is caused by the abrasive influence of fibres during the process of their winding on a bobbin.

The carried research shows that during tensile and especially compression tests of reinforced plastics the strength of glass fibre is not realized in full measure [4] (Table II).

Table II
Compression strength of unidirectional glass plastics,
reinforced by glass fibres with different strength.

No.	Grade of fibre	Aver. strength of fibre kg/mm ²	Compression strength of glass reinf. plast.	Type of resin
1.	Alkali-free alumoborosilicate "E"	280	150	modified epoxy compound
2.	Magnesia-alumosilicate(1)	380	195	
3.	Magnesia-alumosilicate(2)	500	187	
4.	High-modulus of cordierite composition	450	200	

As it is seen from Table II the increase in glass fibre strength alone does not influence compression strength of GRP. Factors influencing this strength are of complicated nature. Compression strength of a compound depends to a great extent on interlayer shift resistance, and thus properties and adhesion of a resin exert a greater influence than mechanical characteristics of glass fibres. Under the influence of compression load the stability loss of fibres at longitudinal bond acquires significance; thus the increase in the diameter of glass fibres raises compression strength of GRP depending on the chemical composition.

Experimental data also prove that high strength of glass fibres is not realized enough in GRP under tension.

It is also ascertained that the modulus of elasticity in a compound has linear dependence on the modulus of elasticity of the glass fibre (Table III).

The data of Table III show that strength and modulus of elasticity of quartz fibres are best realized in GRP. At the same time it is observed that the increase in strength of glass fibres does not additively raise the strength of the compound.

It is to be supposed that the decrease in the strength of glass plastics reinforced with high-strength glass fibres is caused by a number of factors.

1. Unevenness of fibre tension, dispersion of their strength.
2. Non-optimum lengthening of a binder.
3. Exfoliation caused by poor adhesion between the dia and the fibre.

Table III
 Mechanical characteristics of unidirectional glass plastics made of glass fibres
 of different chemical composition and epoxy binder.
 Content of glass in volume 70%.

No.	Grade of fibre dia. 10 μ	Aver. strength of fibre kg/mm ² (from bobbin)	Modulus of elasticity of fibre kg/mm ²	Tensile strength of GRP kg/mm ²		Modulus of elasticity kg/mm ²	
				max.	aver	max.	aver.
1.	Alkali-free alumo-boro- silicate "E"	280	7400	185	175	5800	5500
2.	Magnesia- alumosilicate	500	9300	250	235	7000	6700
3.	"	380	9300	230	220	7200	7000
4.	High-modulus of cordierite composition	450	10500	192	185	7800	7500
5.	Quartz	350	7450	237	225	5200	5000

4. Loss of fibre stability at bend, causing pore formation in the material.
5. Insufficient adhesion of binder to fibres.

Thus in order to increase the strength of high-strength glass fibre compounds it is necessary to carry out further investigations to determine the role of optimum scheme of reinforcement, selection of rational binders and study of surface phenomena on the boundary line between glass and polymers of different chemical compositions.

REFERENCES

1. M.S. Aslanova, *Steklo i Keramika (Glass & Ceramics)*, 4, 1967.
2. M.S. Aslanova, *Verres et refractaires*, 6, 1968.
3. M.S. Aslanova, *Intern. Congress on Glass Vol. X, Japan*, 9, 1974.
4. M.S. Aslanova, *Journ. Intern. Chemic. Soc. von Mendeleev*, Vol. XX, 2, 191, 1975.